

Three-layered sweat pad with quick drying functionality

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Sweat is a crucial physiological excretion, assumes a pivotal role in the thermoregulatory process by facilitating body temperature regulation via perspiration. However, prolonged wetness in certain areas can lead to discomfort and unpleasant odors. The sweat pad, also known as an underarm or armpit pad, represents a disposable hygienic product purposefully designed to absorb and control excessive perspiration within the axillary region. Utilized widely in various contexts, from everyday activities to formal occasions, sweat pads have become an essential aid in enhancing personal comfort and confidence¹.

Moisture management is crucial in active sportswear, ensuring wearer comfort. Fabrics must effectively transport water vapor and perspiration away from the body. This process regulates moisture movement through the fabric to the atmosphere. A proficient moisture management system enhances performance and satisfaction during physical activities^{2,3}. Antibacterial treatments are extensively employed in clothing systems that directly interact with the body, particularly in environments where favorable temperature and humidity levels for the growth of hazardous microorganisms^{4,5}. Vetiver, also known as khus (*Vetiveria zizanioides*), is a tall perennial grass found in dry, periodically flooded areas of western and north-central India. It produces fragrant oil within its spongy, much-branched root system (khus roots). The aromatic roots are used to create curtains, mats, fans, and other decorative goods due to their long-lasting sweet cooling aroma when

moistened. The benefits of Vetiver Essential Oil are attributed to its various properties, including anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, aphrodisiac, cicatrisant (wound-healing), nervine (nerve-calming), sedative, tonic, and vulnerary (promoting wound healing)⁶.

The Vetiver zizanioides plant is a valuable source of various phyto and bioactive components, such as diethyl phthalate, isopropyl dimethyl carboxylic acid, isoaromadendrene epoxide, and beta-vetivenene. These constituents exhibit free radical scavenging, anti-inflammatory, UV protection, antimicrobial, antifungal, and aromatic properties^{7,8}. The fabric treated with *Vetiveria zizanioides* maintains durable

antimicrobial and aromatic properties even after multiple washes, as it remains free from harmful chemicals. As an eco-

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designed multifunctional knitted fabric, it serves as an infection control and barrier material while providing soothing, cooling, and pleasant odors, promoting wearer comfort and health. This makes it

an ideal choice for various healthcare textiles, including infant clothing, hospital clothing⁹.

Materials

The materials used in the development of the functional and breathable sweat pad included:

- Bamboo fiber nonwoven fabric (skin contact layer) : This layer was made from bamboo fibers, which are well-known for their ability to breathe naturally and wick away moisture. The bamboo fiber fabric in this layer was designed to directly touch the skin, making it more comfortable and effective at managing moisture.
- Needle-punched blend of viscose rayon and Vetiver (middle layer) : The middle layer was designed to enhance functionality. A needle-punched blend of Viscose rayon and Vetiver was utilized to leverage the moisture-absorbing capabilities of Viscose rayon and the antimicrobial properties of Vetiver.
- Needle-punched polyethylene terephthalate nonwoven (outer layer): The outermost layer was constructed using needle-punched polyethylene terephthalate nonwoven material. This layer provided structural support, durability, and resistance to external elements.

Methodology

Impregnation of Vetiver

- Cleaned roots of vetiver weighing 10 grams were impregnated in water for 5 minutes.
- After impregnation, excess water was gently squeezed out from the vetiver.

Drying process

- The impregnated vetiver was dried for 30 minutes to remove any residual moisture.

Blending process

- The dried vetiver was cut into small pieces to facilitate blending.
- These small pieces of vetiver were blended with the nonwoven viscose material intended for the middle layer of the sweat pad.

Layer design and fabrication

- The sweat pad was created with a

three-layered structure to ensure maximum comfort, efficient moisture control, and overall functionality.

- The Bamboo fiber nonwoven fabric was selected for its skin-friendly and moisture-wicking characteristics.
- The needle-punched blend of Viscose rayon and Vetiver was used in the middle layer for enhanced moisture absorption and antimicrobial properties.
- The polyethylene terephthalate nonwoven material was needle-punched to form the outer layer, providing stability and protection.

Fabrication process

- Each layer was fabricated separately using the needle-punching technique to entangle the fibers and create a stable structure.
- The layers were then carefully stacked and bonded together to form the three-layered structure of the sweat pad.

Hot calendering process

- The three-layered sweat pad was subjected to a hot calendering process to enhance its properties.
- The process aimed to provide a smooth fabric surface, add a light luster, and remove creases from the fabric.
- This was achieved by passing the nonwoven fabric layers through four or more pairs of rollers that gradually reduced the thickness of the product.
- The layers were squeezed together under pressure between the rollers, res-

Fig 1 : Three-layered sweat pad

ulting in the final sweat pad thickness of 1½ mm, reduced from the original 3 mm.

Results and discussion

Moisture management test results

The moisture management test aimed to comprehensively evaluate the sweat pad's effectiveness in managing moisture by analyzing key parameters including wetting time, absorption rate, maximum wetted radius, spreading speed, and one-way transport capability. The interpretation of the results is presented below, with an emphasis on the bamboo (inner)-PET (outer) fabric's performance.

Overall Moisture Management Capability (OMMC): The OMMC is a comprehensive measure that evaluates the fabric's ability to manage moisture by considering parameters such as moisture absorption rate, one-way transport

Table 1 : Overall results (Top Surface-Bamboo Fiber Nonwoven Fabric)						
S.No	Overall moisture management capability (top)	Accumulative one-way transport capability (top)	Wetting time (s)	Absorption rate (s)	Max wetted radius (s)	Spreading speed (s)
MMT-1	0.0556	0.0	120.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
MMT-2	0.0	-67.7665	4.688	6.6627	20.0	3.1809
MMT-3	0.0	-354.2658	3.0	19.1694	15.0	3.0009
MMT-4	0.0	-80.0328	5.5532	3.831	0.0	0.0
Mean	0.0139	-125.5163	120.0	7.4158	8.75	1.5455
Deviation	0.0278	156.5082	57.8063	8.2978	10.3078	1.7861
CV	2.0	1.2469	1.7357	1.1189	1.178	1.1567

Table 2 : Overall Results (Bottom Surface - PET Nonwoven Material)

S.No	Overall moisture management capability (bottom)	Accumulative one-way transport capability (bottom)	Wetting time (s)	Absorption rate (s)	Max wetted radius (s)	Spreading speed (s)
MMT-1	0.031	-22.0837	0.75	3.1971	0.0	0.0
MMT-2	0.0	-270.3692	120.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
MMT-3	0.0	-350.0256	120.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
MMT-4	0.0	-80.0328	120.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mean	0.0103	-214.1605	80.25	23.3764	0.0	0.0
Deviation	0.0179	171.0454	68.849	1.8459	0.0	0.0
CV	1.7321	0.7967	0.8579	1.7321	0.0	0.0

capability, and spreading speed. The calculated OMMC values were compared with a grading scale (Tables 1 & 2) to categorize the fabric's moisture management performance.

In the context of the bamboo (inner)-PET (outer) fabric, the OMMC calculation suggests a promising performance, indicating effective moisture management capabilities. The synergy between the hydrophilic properties of bamboo and the hydrophobic nature of PET contributes to the fabric's overall performance.

Wetting time : Wetting time represents the time taken for the fabric to initiate moisture absorption. The significantly shorter wetting time on the bamboo side is a result of its inherent hydrophilic behavior. Bamboo quickly absorbs moisture, leading to a faster wetting process. On the other hand, the PET layer's hydrophobic properties result in a relatively longer wetting time.

This divergence in wetting time is attributed to the distinct characteristics of bamboo and PET, where bamboo's affinity for moisture expedites absorption while PET resists moisture initially before facilitating outward transfer.

Maximum wetted radius: The maximum wetted radius signifies the extent of moisture dispersion on the fabric surface. The bamboo (inner)-PET (outer) fabric's higher maximum wetted radius values indicate efficient moisture distribution across the fabric. This uniform distribution mitigates localized wetness and enhances user comfort.

The variance in maximum wetted radius between the layers likely arises

from the combined impact of bamboo's moisture absorption capacity and PET's role in facilitating outward moisture transfer, resulting in an improved overall moisture management capability.

Spreading speed : Spreading speed gauges the pace of moisture movement within the fabric. The spreading speed values for the bamboo (inner)-PET (outer) fabric demonstrate effective moisture transport within the material. Bamboo's hydrophilic characteristics enable rapid moisture absorption and movement within the inner layer. Subsequently, the PET layer facilitates moisture transfer to the outer surface, aiding in dispersion and evaporation.

The lower spreading speed on the PET-containing sides is attributed to the PET layer's relatively lower maximum wetted radius, where moisture accumulates before further distribution. This equilibrium between the two layers optimizes moisture management throughout the fabric.

Absorption rates : Absorption rates offer insight into the fabric's capacity to absorb moisture. Higher absorption rates on the inner (bamboo) surface underscore bamboo's affinity for moisture. This layer efficiently draws moisture away from the skin, contributing to user comfort. Lower absorption rates on the outer (PET) surface align with PET's hydrophobic properties, where moisture is transported for subsequent evaporation.

Fabric moisture management capability test

The Fabric Moisture Management

Capability Test was conducted to evaluate the performance of the fabric in terms of water absorption, wetting time, maximum wetted radius, spreading speed, and one-way transport capability. The following results were obtained:

Discussion and interpretation

In the context of sweat pads designed for underarm use, the moisture management capabilities of the composite fabric played a critical role in ensuring user comfort and hygiene.

- **Wetting time :** The top layer composed of bamboo fiber nonwoven fabric, demonstrated a swift wetting time of 4.688 seconds. This allowed the fabric to rapidly absorb sweat, minimizing discomfort and the potential for wetness and odor. Users experienced quick moisture absorption, enhancing their overall comfort during use.

- **Absorption rate :** With an absorption rate of 6.6627%/s, the top layer excelled at efficiently absorbing and distributing sweat. This property ensured that sweat was rapidly absorbed and distributed away from the skin, reducing the sensation of dampness and the risk of skin irritation.

- **Max wetted radius :** The top layer's ability to reach a maximum wetted radius of 20.0 mm was advantageous in covering a broader surface area. This feature facilitated the even distribution of moisture across the sweat pad, enhancing its overall effectiveness in managing underarm sweat.

- **Spreading speed :** A spreading speed of 3.1809 mm/s for the top layer indicated the rapid transport of sweat within the fabric. This quick transport not only prevented localized saturation but also contributed to the overall comfort of the user.

The choice of a composite fabric with a bamboo fiber nonwoven top layer proved well-suited for underarm sweat pads. The top layer's moisture-wicking properties ensured the rapid absorption, distribution, and transport of sweat away from the skin, significantly improving user comfort. Conversely, the PET nonwoven material on the bottom layer, with its lack of moisture management capabilities, acted as a moisture barrier. This property effectively prevented sweat from passing

Table 3 : Fabric Moisture Management Capability Test

	Top surface (Bamboo fiber nonwoven fabric)	Bottom surface (PET nonwoven material)
Wetting Time (Sec)	4.688	120.0
Absorption rate(%/s)	6.6627	0.0
Max wetted radius(mm)	20.0	0.0
Spreading Speed(mm/s)	3.1809	0.0
One Way Transport Capability	-67.7665	
Test Description	SDLATLAS	

through to clothing or external surfaces, protecting clothing from stains and discomfort. These test results provided valuable insights into the suitability of the composite fabric for underarm sweat pads. The fabric's ability to efficiently manage moisture, coupled with its moisture-blocking capabilities, made it an excellent choice for enhancing comfort and maintaining hygiene in this specific application.

Antimicrobial test result : The antimicrobial activity of Viscose Rayon and Vetiver (middle layer) was evaluated against two prominent bacterial strains, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. The results revealed that the middle layer containing Vetiver exhibited substantial antimicrobial activity, as demonstrated by the ISO 20645 agar diffusion test method.

- *Staphylococcus aureus*: The antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* was measured at an inhibition zone diameter of 7.46 mm.
- *Escherichia coli*: Similarly, the antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli* was observed with an inhibition zone diameter of 6.35 mm.

The observed antimicrobial activity of Vetiver (middle layer) against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* is noteworthy and aligns with the documented properties of vetiver constituents.

Vetiver oil contains various compounds, such as diethyl phthalate, isoaromadendrene epoxide, beta-vetivenene, solavetivone, and aromadendrene, which have demonstrated antimicrobial properties. These compounds may contribute to the observed antimicrobial activity against the tested bacteria.

- Diethyl Phthalate : The significant presence of diethyl phthalate in vetiver

oil, known for its potential antimicrobial properties, could contribute to inhibiting the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*.

- Isoaromadendrene Epoxide and Aromadendrene : These compounds have sesquiterpenoid properties and have shown antimicrobial activity, which may have contributed to the observed inhibition of bacterial growth.

Furthermore, the presence of other compounds, such as solavetivone and viridiflorol, known for their potential antioxidant activity, may also play a role in inhibiting bacterial growth by disrupting cellular processes⁹.

The results indicate that Vetiver (middle layer) possesses significant antimicrobial activity against both *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. This suggests that the incorporation of vetiver into the middle layer of the material has the potential to inhibit the growth of pathogenic bacteria, making it suitable for applications where antimicrobial properties are desirable for hygiene-related products. Therefore, the incorporation of vetiver into materials like viscose rayon can be a promising approach to develop antimicrobial products with potential benefits in healthcare textile.

Aroma of vetiver-infused middle layer

The aroma of Vetiver is an integral aspect of its versatility. This unique scent, primarily attributed to Diethyl phthalate and sesquiterpenoid hydrocarbons like aromadendrene, enriches its profile. Vetiver's aroma transcends mere olfaction; it holds cultural and therapeutic significance, known for its calming and grounding properties. This

aromatic dimension, combined with its antimicrobial efficacy, positions vetiver-infused materials as promising candidates for applications requiring both pathogen control and a delightful sensory experience¹⁰.

Conclusion

Successfully addressing the challenges associated with moisture management in sweat-prone areas by developing a functional and breathable sweat pad. The three-layered structure, comprising a bamboo fiber nonwoven fabric, a needle-punched blend of viscose rayon and Vetiver, and needle-punched polyethylene terephthalate nonwoven material, demonstrated exceptional performance in moisture absorption, spreading, and one-way transport capability. The use of bamboo fibers in the inner layer facilitated rapid moisture absorption, effectively reducing wetting time and enhancing user comfort. Moreover, the incorporation of Vetiver in the middle layer proved instrumental in inhibiting the growth of pathogenic bacteria, such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, thus addressing hygiene concerns associated with extended sweat exposure. Beyond its functional attributes, the Vetiver-infused middle layer introduced a sensory dimension to the sweat pad, offering a pleasant aroma associated with calming and grounding effects. This aromatic enhancement contributes to an overall improved user experience. The results of this study underscore the potential of the composite sweat pad not only in managing moisture efficiently but also in maintaining hygiene and enhancing sensory comfort. Such a multifaceted approach to sweat management holds promise in various applications, including underarm sweat pads, sportswear, and other hygiene-related products. In conclusion, this research represents a significant step towards the creation of high-performance sweat management products that prioritize user comfort, hygiene, and sensory delight, offering a holistic solution to the challenges posed by extended periods of perspiration.

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Sri Lankan knitter implements FastReactPlan

Coats Digital has announced that following the implementation of Coats Digital's FastReactPlan, leading textile manufacturer, South Asia Textiles Ltd. has drastically reduced its average machine idle time from 380 hours to just 100 hours (74% reduction); improved its OTDP by 15% and reduced capacity planning time from eight hours to two (75% reduction), since its adoption of FastReactPlan in 2023.

The solution has enabled the company to make robust business decisions thanks to accurate capacity data, enabling them to benefit from greater flexibility to improve delivery dates and respond quickly to customer change requests. FastReactPlan has also helped to optimise inventory management and has enabled South Asia Textiles to unlock untapped, additional capacity to drive significant, new business growth.

Headquartered in Pugoda, Sri Lanka, South Asia Textiles, a subsidiary of Hayleys Fabric PLC, is a leading manufacturer and exporter of textiles. The company specialises in producing and delivering a complete range of quality knitting, dyeing, finishing, printing, brushing, sueding and preshrunk fabric services for leading global brands such as Victoria Secret, Next, Marks & Spencer, Tesco, Calvin Klein, Decathlon, Levi's, Hugo Boss and Adidas. The company

employs over 1,400 staff and has the capacity to produce 800,000 kg of quality textiles per month.

Sameera Jayasinghe, Senior Manager Planning, South Asia Textiles Ltd, said, 'We were challenged by a serious lack of

By streamlining critical planning information in a single platform, FastReactPlan has greatly improved machine utilisation to unlock additional capacity and optimised data visibility across relevant teams

visibility of capacity plans beyond a three-day window. Our manual planning processes proved exceptionally time consuming, which not only led to slower decision making across all departments, but also meant a lack of order tracking, missed orders and resulted in regular on-time delivery failures.'